

FORMING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN BASED ON VALUES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of values in introducing preschool children to values and improving the spiritual and moral qualities of preschool children.*

Keywords: *value, world, cultural, spirituality, homeland, love, peace, freedom, people, pedagogue, modern, psychology, education.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ДУХОВНО-ПРАВСТВЕННЫХ КАЧЕСТВ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается роль ценностей в приобщении детей дошкольного возраста к ценностям и совершенствовании духовно-нравственных качеств детей дошкольного возраста.*

Ключевые слова: *ценность, мир, культура, духовность, родина, любовь, мир, свобода, народ, педагог, современный, психология, образование.*

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As we know, preschool education covers children from 3 to 7 years old. By the age of 5, a child can acquire 90 percent of information about the world. The correct upbringing of the growing younger generation, both physically, spiritually and morally, should be implemented in every family, following the recommendations of modern medicine, pedagogy, and psychology. The role of not only the educator, but especially the family in the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in a child is very important. As our wise people say, a bird does what it sees in its nest. From this it is known that the child receives the initial spiritual and moral education from the family.

As our first President Islam Karimov said, "High spirituality is an invincible force." The term spiritual education in a broad sense means a set of spiritual influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at ensuring the active participation of a person in social, spiritual, and educational life. Moral education is understood as a system of scientific and practical actions aimed at forming human qualities in the growing generation that meet the standards of morality and meet the requirements of the times. The role of moral education in the future of a child is incomparable.

Each nation has its own traditions, national values. Our state, Uzbekistan, is also a state rich in its national values.

The term value is a broad concept, a concept that indicates the universal, socio-moral, cultural, spiritual significance of certain phenomena in reality. All things that are important for a person and humanity, for example, freedom, peace, justice, enlightenment, truth, goodness, material and spiritual wealth, etc. are considered values.

It is clear from this that we need to enrich the minds and thinking of the growing younger generation with our nationality and educate them with our values. Our greatest values, our priceless blessings, are our peace and freedom. Preschool children should be educated in the spirit of love for their homeland. We need to explain to children what the concepts of peace and freedom mean and show them in practice. First of all, we must explain to the younger generation about the motherland, how sacred the concept of the homeland is, how the motherland is the land where our umbilical cord blood was shed, and the great place where our great ancestors left their traces, and we must also educate the younger generation in the spirit of love for the homeland.

Because, in every person who understands the meaning and content of this great concept of peace, the greatest concept of appreciating peace and serving to preserve our peace will arise.

In the younger generations who understand the essence of these great concepts such as peace, freedom, and homeland, a great concept will emerge: to serve the motherland, to raise the flag of our homeland even higher, to turn our homeland into an even stronger state, and to create a more perfect and great future for our homeland. And a person who takes these concepts to heart will certainly find the strength to do all of this.

In conclusion, we must enrich the spiritual world of preschool children with our national values. From each young generation educated and raised with our national values, great generations will grow up who love their homeland, who will take their homeland to greater heights, who will turn their homeland into the most powerful and developed state, and who will create a great future for their homeland. A democratic country, its future is in the hands of young people.

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